

Experiments of Human-Robot Teaming under Sliding Autonomy

Fang Tang, Mahmood Mohammed, and Jacob Longazo

Abstract—This paper describes a sliding autonomy approach for coordinating a team of robots to assist the human operator to accomplish tasks while adapting to new or unexpected situations by requesting help from the human operator. While sliding autonomy has been well studied in the context of controlling a single robot. Much work needs to be done to apply sliding autonomy to a multi-robot team, especially human-robot team. Our approach extends the traditional sliding autonomy by including a new mode that support human-robot peer-to-peer collaboration. We validated our approach in the USARSim simulation and on physical robots, and demonstrated that the human-robot team’s overall performance can be improved under the sliding autonomy control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-robot systems are widely used in today’s robotic applications because of their advantages over single robot systems [1], such as improvements in robustness, reliability and efficiency. Increased autonomy will reduce human intervention, thus reduce the operating cost and increase human safety. However, challenges also arise with this type of complex system, such as mechanisms for coordinating team members, fault tolerance of the team and the operator control of the team. While researchers strive to build a fully autonomous system to perform various tasks, the robot team inevitably faces many unforeseen circumstances in an open and dynamic world. The team can either adapt to the dynamics through some life-long learning process, or by seeking help from the more competent human operator. Our goal is to develop a human-robot team with collaborative robots assisting the human operator to accomplish tasks while adapting to new or unexpected situations with the help from the human operator.

As a motivating example, consider a site clearing task that requires a specific area to be cleared of obstacles, which we simplify to be box-shape obstacles with different weights or sizes. The objective of the task is to clear the site in as little time as possible. The task can be decomposed into a series of subtasks with each removing one obstacle. We assume there is a general planner that determines the ordering constraints of subtasks. Note that obstacles come with different weights, and thus may require multiple robots to push them depending on the capabilities of the robots (e.g., push forces) and the weight of the box. When multiple robots are needed, they need to work closely with each other to manipulate the box to the goal location. We expect that robots can accomplish the tasks autonomously most of the time. However, human operator may be needed to help the robots in special situations. For example, when the sensor on

a robot is obstructed by a piece of cloth, wheels get stuck, or extra forces are needed to push a heavy box.

Our approach to the above problem is to apply sliding autonomy to control the multi-robot team. Our sliding autonomy approach features levels of control from fully autonomous operations, to human-intervened operations and pure teleoperation. Additionally, there is a great potential for human and robots to work together side by side and for each team member to contribute to the task objective based on their capabilities. thus, we introduce a peer-to-peer interaction mode for the human operator to work closely with the robot team as peers rather than just as supervisors.

Our sliding autonomy control interface allows human operators to monitor the task execution status, intervene to improve efficiency and react to unforeseen issues. It also enables the system to seamlessly switch between different levels of control. It helps establish the interaction between humans and robots by allowing them to influence each other’s action selection and decision making.

The goal of this research is to build a low-cost ground station that enables interoperability between multiple robots and a single human operator without putting a heavy load on the operator. The major contribution of this work lies in the following areas: 1) the introduction of peer-to-peer interaction mode to sliding autonomy; 2) the development of a simulation experimentation testbed for sliding autonomy; and 3) the physical experiment to demonstrate peer-to-peer interaction under sliding autonomy. We validated our proposed sliding autonomy approach on the site clearing task using the USARSim simulator [2] and on physical robots. We demonstrated that our system can easily switch between different levels of controls. The overall team performance can be improved over pure autonomy.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. We discuss the related work in Section II and describe the details of our approach in Section III. In Section IV, experiments are performed to validate our approach. We finally conclude our work in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

Sliding autonomy has been widely used in controlling a single robot. It was also referred to as adjustable autonomy [4] and mixed initiative teaming [5] in earlier work. The paper in [4] describes the potential use of adjustable autonomy in space missions. The motivation of peer-to-peer interaction rather than supervisory interaction has been presented in [5]. In some cases, the system is composed of discrete autonomy levels, varying from pure teleoperation to full autonomy of robots. In other cases, the system is composed of a sliding

Department of Computer Science, California State Polytechnic University Pomona, 3801 W. Temple Ave., Pomona, CA ftang@cpp.edu

autonomy levels which can be decided by varying a set of parameters. As an example, the work in [6] describes how human inputs and robot inputs can be combined to generate a dynamic mode between the two extreme modes of autonomy and teleoperation.

More research works started applying sliding autonomy to control multiple robots. According to [7], when a human operator needs to control a multi-robot team, it is more efficient if robots have coordinated control rather than manual control. They also used the USARSim for their experiments, but used a different controller than ours. The work in [8] performed four experiments to compare the sequential management style with the playbook management style when controlling multiple robots and showed that adjustable autonomy can improve the performance of both styles.

Our work is based on the sliding autonomy approach introduced in [9]. This research work breaks the sliding control into four modes of pure autonomy, mixed-initiative, system-initiative and teleoperation. They explored the issues of how to apply sliding autonomy to a multi-robot team by enabling the robots to request for help, bringing extra situation awareness and maintaining coordination of the team. They applied their control approach to a multi-robot assembly problem, which requires coordination among heterogeneous robots. Different from this work, our work introduces a new component of peer-to-peer interaction mode.

The work in [10] also introduced peer-to-peer human-robot interaction into the sliding autonomy. Based on the work in [9] and [11], they identified six capabilities for enabling sliding autonomy on a treasure hunt task. Their experiments showed that sliding autonomy can improve team performance by allowing different team configurations (including the human operator) to accomplish the same task. Our work also addresses the similar issue but with a different perspective.

III. THE APPROACH

A. Sliding Autonomy

Our approach to sliding autonomy implements different levels of interactions to enable the human operator and the robot team to accomplish a task in a collaborative manner. Under sliding autonomy, the system can dynamically switch between autonomy, semi-autonomy, teleoperation, and peer-to-peer interaction modes depending on the situation. The different levels or modes represent an increasing level of human involvement in task execution. By default, all robots start in an autonomous mode. Full autonomy is most desirable when the robots have the capabilities to handle the task with efficiency. However, we also recognize that robots work in a dynamic world with unforeseen uncertainties, which cannot be easily handled with an autonomous solution. Thus, human operators can assist the operation of robots at critical times when robots face irresolvable issues. They can change the mode of operations at anytime when an autonomous mode has a degraded performance or fails, see Figure 1.

The operator gets to select the appropriate level of control depending on his/her work load and the status of task

Fig. 1. Sliding Autonomy of Controls. Here, failure can be triggered either by the robot or the operator.

execution. Our goal is not to overload the operator’s job; especially when a single operator needs to attend to the entire multi-robot team rather than a few robots. In a semi-autonomous mode, a human operator is typically expected to share critical information with the robots (e.g., a new waypoint) or provide minimum guidance or assessment on the current situation (e.g. the camera view is blocked). Thus it only requires bounded levels of human interaction but not full attention. The human operator can still multi-task while helping the individual robot. The teleoperation mode provides more precise control by constantly sending direct commands and controls, it however requires operator’s full attention. There is also the challenge of providing enough situation awareness.

For cases that robots cannot handle solely by themselves even with the shared information or direct control, the human operator will need to physically work with the robots as peers to accomplish the task. We include this peer-to-peer mode in our model, which is the mode that will require the operator’s full attention and mechanisms for the peers to communicate and interact with each other. No matter what mode the robot is in, the system will resume in an autonomous mode after the problem is resolved. The core concept behind the sliding autonomy approach is to combine the control methods of both autonomy and teleoperation in a way that best highlights each control method’s advantages.

To enable the switch between different operation modes, the human operator will oversee the execution of the entire team via a graphical interface on a base station. Each robot will also constantly monitor its own task execution. If a robot detects a certain error condition that it cannot recover from while under the autonomy mode, it can request help from a human operator to guide it to a condition the system can recover from. The human operator can also dismiss the request if he/she is currently busy with other higher priority jobs. Meanwhile, if the human operator observes a robot behaving incorrectly or inefficiently, the human operator can intervene the control of the robot to improve its behavior.

The ability of both the robot and the operator to issue a control switch helps the system respond to many types of situation. To better describe the two modes described

above, we use similar terms as in [9]. The semi-autonomous mode is further defined as: 1) System-Initiative: Only the robot can initiate a switch when it detects that it is in an erroneous state; and 2) Mixed-Initiative: Either the robot (error detection) or the human can initiate a switch (judgment).

With sliding autonomy, we expect that the robots can behave autonomously most of the time with occasional requests for cooperation at critical time, thus very few human operators and little operation time are expected. This type of system should solve the problems of full autonomy and teleoperation without the associated drawbacks of the two. With the addition of the peer-to-peer interaction mode, we augment the traditional sliding autonomy to handle more complex situations when the other modes do not meet the requirement.

To apply the sliding autonomy mechanism to a multi-robot application with requirement for tightly-coupled cooperation, we also need to include other components to facilitate the human robot collaboration and communication between multiple robots. We describe these components in the following sections.

B. Human-Robot Communication

In our proposed approach, human and robots communicate both explicitly and implicitly. Human operators and robots exchange information depending on different levels of interaction between them. Data communication is bidirectional. At a high level, operators assign tasks to robots with task specification such as defining the goal position for the robots to achieve. Robots inform operators of their current task-execution status, for example, informing the operator the completion of its current task. At a low level, the operator may teleoperate robots through direct commands, or exchange sensing or computational information with robot as needed.

Additionally, robots inform the operator of their possible failures so that the operator can assist them in assessing or recovering from the failures. Based on the flow of information that are required to accomplish a task, humans and robots can communicate information with each other when necessary. For example, an operator can help a robot find its way home by teleoperating it with direct commands or giving the relative goal position to the robot. The information exchange between operators and robots depends on the various interfaces with which they communicate. We developed a basic graphical interface to facilitate the communication including components such as command and control, dialogue and vision.

C. Peer-to-Peer Interaction

When multiple robots work collaboratively as peers, we often rely on explicit communication when communication is reliable and bandwidth is abundant. However, in the case of human robot collaboration, explicit communication is difficult since it will require the operator to carry a wearable or portable device with him/her, which will make it harder for

the operator to interact with the robot. It is also more natural for humans to communicate through dialogue or observation rather than reading some encoded messages. Thus, we apply implicit communication when the operator interacts with the robot(s) as peers. The operator can observe the status of task and the robots since they directly work together at the task site. Robots can also observe the status of the task or the actions of the operators through sensory feedback.

Passive communication is always a challenging task for the robots. We rely on the environment to provide the media of communication. When pushing a long box in our site clearing scenario, two robots are required to push the box on its two ends in turns in order to maintain the box's orientation and trajectory. With explicit communication, we can have the robots send each other a message once it has pushed the box on one end and thus signals the push on the other end. With implicit communication, we need to add a new capability on the robot such that it can recognize that the a long box has been pushed on one side by a human operator or another robot. The detection works by finding the degree of change in the box's relative position to the robot. When the degree of change passes a certain threshold, it means the other end has been pushed. Furthermore, we also enable the robot to have a voice feedback to communicate through sounds when the human operator is pushing too fast or too slow.

D. Task Allocation

To handle multiple tasks of pushing obstacles, we implement a basic task allocation approach based on the Contract Net Protocol [13]. Here is the process:

- 1) Task announcement: Initially, the human operator introduces the site clearing task T to an "Auctioneer" agent built in the operator control interface. Assuming there's a planner to decompose the task into subtasks and save them in a task queue. The auctioneer then announces the subtask one at a time to the robots. Each subtask t_i holds task specific information, such as the weight, the position of the obstacle to be removed and the destination.
- 2) Bid submission: Each idle robot submits a bid to the auctioneer including its current distance from the obstacle and its pushing forces.
- 3) Winner determination: Once bids are collected, the auctioneer then uses a greedy approach to determine the winning robot(s) for the current task. The winning robot(s) should have a summed force (f_{sum}) greater than the weight of the box. There are further two preferences. First, we favor robots that are closer to the obstacle and thus ensures fast completion time. Second, we try to minimize f_{sum} so that we allocate as little resources as possible to execute the current tasks. Unsuccessful allocation will result in the subtask being reinserted back to the task queue.

When multiple robots are allocated to the same task, they collaborate to push the box to the final destination. If a robot fails during the collaboration, its team member will inform the failure to the ground station. The operator can either

Fig. 2. Our site clearing task simulated with three robots with the checkers) and five obstacles (solid color) using USARSim.

reinsert the task back to the task queue and set the rest of the team members to be idle, or manually allocate another agent (robot or human) to complete the task.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

To validate our approach, we applied our approach to both simulated robots and physical robots with the site clearing task. Simulation allows us to demonstrate the smooth transitions between different modes of operation (except for peer-to-peer interaction) under sliding autonomy. While the physical experiment allows us to demonstrate the effectiveness of the peer-to-peer interaction mode.

A. Simulation

1) *Simulation Setup:* Our simulation used USARSim [2], a high-fidelity, extensible simulation developed to facilitate human-robot interaction in the search and rescue domain. Our task involves a team of three robots working cooperatively to push obstacles against two opposite walls in the test room (see Figure 2). The robots are equipped with an INS sensor to help the robot determine its position and direction using wheel encoders. We set it such that the INS sensor is subject to drifting, causing accumulated errors over time. It is also equipped with a laser range finder for obstacle or box detection.

We chose an open source controller application Iridium that's compatible with USARSim. Iridium, however, only provides some basic features for controlling a single robot. We have heavily extended Iridium to act as each robot's simulated control system with capabilities for teleoperation, navigation, obstacle avoidance, box detection and additional UDP communications. The Iridium controllers are also given the ability to act as a bidder for task allocation. To support sliding autonomy, the controller also includes functionalities such as detecting erroneous situations in which to request human aid; returning to autonomous mode after a problem is resolved, and human-intervened control at any point.

A central controller interface (HUB), contains the task auctioneer, teleoperation controls, as well as a graphical user interface that allows it to control the simulation and all its various components. The user interface is developed using

Fig. 3. A typical run of the site clearing task. Time reported: minutes:seconds:milliseconds.

TABLE I

SAMPLE INFO LOG MESSAGES SENT TO THE OPERATOR.

Msg. Type	Example
Status	Task 1 Assigned 00:59:28
Status	Task Completed: Task 1 01:49:96
Error	Teleoperation Request: R2 error: stuck 00:02:25
Error	Teleoperation Request: R1 error: Timeout 00:20:36
Error	Teleoperation Request: R2 error: Missed Box 01:47:94

the Qt software [12]. Qt was selected for its cross platform capability as well as its extensive libraries. The operator can monitor status of robot execution through the INFO LOG window and change the autonomy mode.

2) *Simulation Results:* We have tested our sliding autonomy approach with an autonomous mode, a system-initiative mode, a mixed-initiative mode and a teleoperation mode. A robot will initiate a request for help when it enters an erroneous state. For example, when a robot has taken too long to complete a task, it will trigger a timeout and a request for help. An error message is sent to the HUB (e.g., stuck, expected completion time exceeded, see Table I). When the HUB got the message, it would change the robot's status on the user interface to show the error and notify the operator. The operator would typically intervene in situations such as when two robots are on a collision course; the robot didn't quite line up well with the boxes (causing a box to get pushed diagonally); or if the collision avoidance behaves erratically. Figure 3 shows the time line of a typical run with the various events.

To measure the performance of our sliding autonomy control, one expert user and one novice user each performed ten trials under every control mode. We collected data on completion time (in seconds), solution quality and operator workload. When measuring solution quality, one point is awarded for a box being pushed close enough to the wall, a half point awarded for incomplete pushes, and 2 points for completion time of under 5 minutes. The operator workload

Fig. 4. The iRobot Create robot and the testing environment.

TABLE II
EXPERIENCED OPERATOR (EO) vs. NOVICE OPERATOR (NO)

Operation Mode	Time	Solution Quality	Workload
	EO vs. NO	EO vs. NO	EO vs. NO
Autonomy	176 vs. 176	72% vs. 72%	0 vs. 0
System Initiative	189 vs. 176	96% vs. 95%	34 vs. 31
Mixed Initiative	180 vs. 176	100% vs. 98%	52 vs. 34
Teleoperation	253 vs. 241	100% vs. 100%	62 vs. 43

is determined by having the operator fill out the NASA TLX (Task Load Index) Survey [14], with scores ranging between 1 and 100. The data in this area is very subjective, but still shows expected trends. Table II compared the averaged results of using sliding autonomy control by an experienced operator and a novice operator respectively.

From the experimental results, we could see the improvement of using sliding autonomy over the fully autonomous systems. The different levels of control allows the system to deal with degraded performance as well as faulty conditions. There is an increase in solution quality from autonomy to system-initiative, mixed-initiative and teleoperation modes, but also with an increasing workload on the human operator and more time for completion. Comparing the system-initiative mode with the mixed-initiative mode, we notice that when the operator has the ability to intervene early, the overall solution quality can be improved, and so is the completion time, with an increasing workload. We expect that teleoperation has the best solution quality but the worst completion time and workload. The autonomous mode has the best completion time and workload but the worst solution quality. The other two modes sit in between autonomy and teleoperation.

B. Physical Robot Experiments

1) *Physical Experimental Setup*: We also designed physical experiments to demonstrate the feasibility of our approach with a focus on the peer-to-peer interaction mode. The robot we used is an iRobot Create robot equipped with a Hokuyo laser range finder, and an Acer netbook equipped with a camera. We use the laser range finder to detect the box

Fig. 5. The graphical user interface used on physical robots.

and the camera to locate the goal location (an orange blob). The goal of the task is for the robot(s) to push the box to the goal location with no obstacles on the course (see Figure 4). We use the open source Robot Operating System (ROS) [15] as our robot controller. We also designed a control interface using Qt (see Figure 5).

For the sliding control, we designed it such that the robot can switch between autonomous, teleoperation and peer-to-peer mode. All robots start with the autonomous mode. The operator will constantly observe the execution status and decide to select the appropriate operation mode. The operator can intervene at anytime to switch modes, while the robot(s) can also initiate a help request. Robots can also resume autonomous mode at anytime if the operator decides to switch back from other modes.

In our implementation, the robot uses its laser range finder to detect the box and navigate to it once it has been allocated the task. As shown in Figure 6 a and b, the detection process works by moving to the nearest object based on its laser scan, then detecting and moving to the ends of the box. Here we assume that the box is large enough and it will require two agents to push on each end. Both agents also need to coordinate their behaviors such that the box orientation remains about the same. To enable the peer-to-peer interaction between the operator and the robot, both agents use passive communication when they push the box together. The robot constantly updates the relative angle of the box, when the angle of change passes a certain threshold, the robot considers that the box has been pushed on the other side.

Due to the lack of a second robot, we only demonstrated the autonomous and teleoperation modes with a single robot. In the peer-to-peer mode, two robots are supposed to push the box, we simulate a robot break down before they start pushing, which will trigger an error message been sent to the human operator to request for help. The operator will then choose to accept or deny the request. Accepting the request will make the robot wait for the operator for a period of time before finding another agent (robot or human) who is willing to help. In our test, we assume the operator will accept the request immediately and start working with the robot to push

Fig. 6. The physical demonstration of the peer-to-peer mode: a) A robot moves towards the box. b) The robot reaches one end of the box and asks for help, and waits for the operator to push on the other side. c) The robot and the operator push the box together to reach the goal (unfortunately the operator was not photographed in the process).

TABLE III
PHYSICAL EXPERIMENTS RESULTS

Operation Mode	Completion Time	Success Rate	Workload
Teleoperation	Worst (160s)	Best (100%)	Worst (> 120s)
Autonomous	Good (90s)	Worst (40%)	Best (0s)
Peer-to-Peer	Best (50s)	Better (80%)	Good (30s)

the box together towards the goal.

2) *Results:* We ran each mode 5 times and averaged the results. Table III showed the completion time, success rate and operator workload for each operation mode. The workload is measured by the amount of time that requires an active participation of the human operator. There are many factors that can influence the success rate of the execution. For example, the box gets pushed off the course during the execution and the robots fail to detect it. Additionally, in the autonomous mode with a single robot, it was difficult to push the box along a straight line towards the goal and we had to constantly adjust the course. This is due to the fact that the robot is of a round shape and it is relatively difficult to find the right point on the box to push such that its orientation would be maintained.

As a result, teleoperation has the highest success rate, however, the robot is hard to teleoperate and thus takes the longest time to complete the task. Teleoperation also requires full operation attention for execution. The autonomous mode has the lowest success rate with an average completion time due to the fact that it is relatively difficult for one robot to push a large box. While peer-to-peer mode has a better success rate and completion time because the human operator can help the robot to push the large box together in a more effective way.

From the physical experiments, we showed that a single operator can flexibly switch between different modes to help

the robots when necessary. By incorporating the peer-to-peer mode, we also showed that the team can improve its performance and even deal with situations that robots cannot handle by themselves.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have described our sliding autonomy approach to solve the site clearing task. The human operator can monitor the status of the execution through the a graphical control interface and intervene the operation at anytime to improve performance. The robots can also initiate a request for operator's participation. We validated our approach in the USARSim simulation and also demonstrated the peer-to-peer interaction mode on physical robots.

As a future work, we will extend our current sliding autonomy approach with more sophisticated mechanisms for the robot to decide when and how to initiate help. We would like to extend the peer-to-peer interaction mode to enable dialogue and speech recognition between the operators and robots. We would like to enhance the current graphical control interface to provide more situation awareness. Additionally, we plan to develop the control interface on portable devices such as cell phones or tablets such that human operators can carry them while interacting with the robots.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. E. Parker. Distributed Intelligence: Overview of the Field and its Application in Multi-Robot Systems. *Journal of Physical Agents, Special Issue on Multi-Robot Systems*, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2008.
- [2] M. Lewis, J. Wang, and S. Hughes. USARSim: Simulation for the Study of Human-Robot Interaction. *Journal of Cognitive Engineering and Decision Making*, 2007.
- [3] B. Gerkey and M. J. Mataric. A Formal Analysis and Taxonomy of Task Allocation in Multi-Robot Systems. *International Journal of Robotics Research*, Vol. 23, No. 9, 2004.
- [4] G. Dorais, R. Banasso, et al. Adjustable Autonomy for Human-Centered Autonomous Systems on Mars. In *Proceedings of the Mars Society Conference*, 1998.
- [5] J. Marble, D. Bruemmer, et al. Evaluation of Supervisory vs. Peer-To-Peer Interaction with Human-Robot Teams. In *Proceedings of the Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 2004.
- [6] M. Desai and H. A. Yanco. Blending Human and Robot Inputs for Sliding Scale Autonomy. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Workshop on Robots and Human Interactive Communication*, 2005.
- [7] J. Wang, M. Lewis, and P. Scerri. Cooperating Robots For Search and Rescue. In *Proceedings of AAMAS*, 2005.
- [8] M. A. Goodrich, T. W. McLain, et al. Managing Autonomy in Robot Teams: Observations From Our Experiments. In *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*, 2007.
- [9] B. Sellner, F. Heger, et al. Coordinated Multi-Agent Teams and Sliding Autonomy for Large-Scale Assembly. In *Proceedings of the IEEE*, Vol. 94, No. 7, 2006.
- [10] M. B. Dias, B. Kannan, et al. Sliding Autonomy for Peer-To-Peer Human-Robot Teams. In *Proceedings of the 10th Intelligent Conference on Intelligent Autonomous Systems*, 2008.
- [11] D. J. Bummer and M. Walton. Collaborative Tools for Mixed Teams of Humans and Robots. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Multi-Robot Systems*, 2003.
- [12] Qt Project. www.qt-project.org.
- [13] R. Smith. The Contract-Net Protocol: High-Level Communication and Control in a Distributed Problem Solver. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 1980.
- [14] S. G. Hart and L. E. Staveland. Development of the NASA-TLX (task load index): Results of Empirical and Theoretical Research. *Human Mental Workload*, 1988.
- [15] Robot Operating System. wiki.ros.org.